

Praja Mitra Mandali: A Re –Appraisal

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Abstract

Praja Mitra mandali which was established in 1917 in the princely state of Mysore played an important role in bringing awareness among the non Brahmins. It was the first non Brahmin organization the state. Sahukar Chennaiah, M Basavaiah, and a host of others through this organization tried to bring political awareness among the backward classes through which they were able to achieve social justice. An attempt is made in this paper to trace growth and development of Praja Mitra Mandali and its attempts in both political and social arena of the princely State of Mysore.

Keywords: Sahukar Chennaiah, M. Basavaiah, Praja Mitra Mandali, Justice Miller Commission, Sir M.Vishveshwaraiah, Diwan Kantharaj Urs, Krishan Raja Wodeyar IV

While speaking about the rise of nationalism and debates over social reform issues, it is noteworthy to mention that all the parts of Karnataka did not react same. The provinces under Bombay presidency which fell under the influence of Tilak reacted intensely to the situation, whereas the reactions of provinces under the rule of Nizam of Hyderabad was very poor. The largest Kannada speaking population was in the princely state of Mysore. Being seen both direct and indirect rule, the socio-political conditions in Mysore were different. During the direct rule (1831-1881) many progressive works like introduction of railway were started. After the rendition in 1881, the administration was under the vigilance of the Diwans. Under the Progressive Diwans like Rangacharlu and K. Sheshadri Iyyer Mysore continued its march towards progress. The establishment of ‘Mysore Representative Assembly’ in 1881 provided a state level platform for the leaders to discuss the socio-political issues. All social-political activities of British India naturally had its impact on the princely state of Mysore also.

By the time of Swami Vivekananda’s entry the social reform issues like ‘infant marriage regulation act’ were in the hot seat of debate. Newspapers like Karnataka Prakashika, Mysore Vrittanta Bodhini led the cause of social reformation. All these factors influenced the social-political conditions of the state which finally led to the growth and development of the backward classes movement. The mouth piece of this movement was Praja Mitra Mandali.

Praja Mitra Mandali founded in the year 1917 was the first Non-Brahmin Political party in the state and it played an important role

in rousing the political consciousnesses among the masses of the people of the state. It voiced the grievances of the common mass and made them to fight for their political right especially in their share in administrative services and their participation in political institutions. The re appraisal of the role played by the Praja Mitra Mandali is based on contemporary news papers, proceedings of the Representative Assembly and Legislative Council, Private papers collections of some important non Brahmin leaders of the time and along with many secondary sources.

The backward classes which constituted nearly 90% of the population had not been given proper representation in administration. The main reason for their backwardness was the lack of education. This also resulted in not having proper representation in legislative bodies and government services. The social-political factors which are mentioned earlier had a great influence and finally to the organization. Some leaders like C.R.Reddy, Abul Khami and a host of others were the pioneers of the organization.

The first meeting of the backward classes in princely Mysore was held in November 1917 at Bangalore under the presidentship of Annaswami Mudaliyar. M. Basavaiah, the then prominent leader of non-Brahmin communities actively participated in organizing the meeting. He held that the political voice of 90 % of the people should be heard by the government and adequate representation should be given in administrative services and legislative bodies. Basavaiah called upon the backward classes people to organize themselves and to demand their rights and safeguard their interests.

To represent their grievances, the leaders like Basavaiah, Annaswami Mudaliyar, C.R.Reddy, Abul Khami felt the need for an organization of their own. Hence, at a meeting held on December 6, 1916 they founded the 'Praja Mitra Mandali' the first political party in the state. Rao Saheb H. Chennaiah became the first president and M. Basavaiah as its first organizing secretary. Mohammud Abdul Kalami, D.Banumaiah, Mohammad Abbas Khan, M.Subbaiah and a host of others constituted the executive committee. The executive committee of the Praja Mitra Mandali met in February 1917 at Bangalore under the presidentship of H. Chennaiah and was attended by representatives from different parts of the state. They decided to submit a memorandum to the H.H. Maharaja about their demands for equal representation of all communities in various bodies including administration. They published a manifesto demanding facilities for the spread of education among all the backward communities and representation in the government services on the basis of population. A branch of Praja Mitra Mandali was started in Mysore in February 1918 and the objectives of the Mandali were designed at the meeting.

The Praja Mitra Mandali submitted a memorandum to the H.H. Maharaja in June 1918 demanding him to undo the injustice done to the backward classes. For a long time, the question of adequate representation of all communities in the public service of the state had engaged in the government. Then Mysore state was ruled by H.H. Maharaja Nalwadi Krishna Raja Wodeyar. Sir. M. Vishveshwaraiah was the Dewan. Maharaja on the one hand was in favor of the majority of his subject, whereas on the other hand Dewan was in favor of Merit, irrespective of his caste or community. More over it was the time of first world war. The economic-social impact of the world war I on the state of Mysore was immense. Any how Mysore economy was able to survive under the effective Dewanship of Sir. M Vishveshwaraiah.

In reply to the memorandum submitted by the leaders of the Praja Mitra Mandali, the government of Mysore felt the need of a comprehensive review of the situation and for taking definite measures for the increased representation of the backward classes. The government of Maharaja appointed a committee under the chairmanship of Leslie. C. Miller to suggest the remedial measures. It is popularly known as Miller Committee. This was the first major achievement of the Praja Mitra Mandali. The miller committee submitted its report in July 1919. After careful consideration the

government decided to attempt ‘ a definite standard of representation of the backward communities in the public services’ and decided that the proportion of the members of the backward communities should be gradually raised to 50% of the total strength within seven years. The setup of Miller Committee finally led to the resignation of Sir. M Vishveshwaraiah from Dewanship.

After Miller Committee report was accepted by the Government and orders were issued and implemented the government orders thereon, the situation in regard to representation of backward classes in government services improved substantially . that was an important achievement of the Praja Mitra Mandali.

The Praja Mitra Mandali reached a definite stage of its agitation when it organized the first state wide backward classes conference at Mysore in October 1929 under the presidentship of Arcot Ramswami MUDaliyar. The conference took the stand that the backward classes people should participate effectively in administration by getting adequate representation in different departments of the public service. The president declared that the movement was born to do away with the social inequalities and obstacles to progress and to elevate the masses. He held that the movement was a social revolt against the fossilized India.

Conclusion

whenever we study the social history of modern Mysore one cannot forget the role of Praja Mitra Mandali. As it was the first non-Brahmin organization which had a strong influence of Madras Presidency, was successful in organizing the backward classes in to a institution. As a result the Miller Committee was appointed and rest is history. But in late 1930 the generation gap in the organization led to the establishment of Praja Paksha. Few youth who were not satisfied with the way in which the Mandali was working, came out from the organization and established the new Praja Paksha. Finally in 1930 both were merged in to Samyukata Praja Paksha and led to the establishment of Mysore Congress.

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